

Modification by measurement: insight into local temperature disturbance when using contact skin temperature sensors

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Introduction

When using contact temperature sensors to quantify human skin temperature (T_{sk}), the sensor used will ideally 1) cause negligible modification of local T_{sk} (compared to when the sensor is not present) and 2) come to an equilibrium temperature that is close to that of the underlying skin. Clarifying whether, or under what conditions, non-trivial errors manifest can assist users to make informed decisions about the relevance of these errors for a given application and can inform the design of future sensor systems. The aim of this work was to use a physical skin model to characterise the differences between the unmodified temperature, modified temperature, and the surface temperature measured using human T_{sk} sensors.

Methods

A skin simulant was made using polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) elastomer [Sylgard 170; Dow Corning, USA; thermal conductivity ~ 0.23 W/(m·K)] with small thermistors (diameter 0.8 mm; type B57540G1, 10 k Ω ; Epcos AG, Germany) embedded within 1 mm of the surface. Temperature control was established using a water-perfused aluminium plate. A schematic is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic of the skin model with a conventional T_{sk} sensor on the surface and a reference temperature sensor directly below the surface.

Measurements were performed in an environmental chamber with air temperature $23.8 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$; air velocity was provided by fans parallel to the model surface, with the air velocity ~ 0.5 m/s ~ 15 mm above the model surface. The subsurface temperature of the model (uncovered state) was maintained at $31.93 \pm 0.02^\circ\text{C}$. A series of measurements were performed with three different T_{sk} sensors ($n=5$ replicates for each) attached to the surface directly above a sub-surface temperature sensor. The T_{sk} sensors were: Maxim iButtons (DS1922L, Maxim Integrated Inc., USA), Grant thermistors (EUS-U-VS5-0, Grant Instruments Ltd., UK), and custom thermistors, consisting of a small thermistor (type B57550G1, 10 k Ω ; diameter 1.3 mm; Epcos AG, Germany) set inside a small volume of the same PDMS used for the skin model. This custom sensor was made with minimal distance between the sensing component (thermistor) and the contact measurement surface and minimal mass around the sensing component. A nonwoven medical tape was used to attach sensors to the measurement surface (Hypafix 16002; BSN Medical, Germany; thickness, 0.25 ± 0.03 mm; mass-per-unit area, 76 ± 1 g·m⁻²). Prior to the experiment, all temperature sensors were calibrated over the range of 15–40°C (OptiCal calibration chamber; Kelvimat 4323 reference thermometer).

For each temperature measurement (covered and uncovered subsurface temperature; T_{sk} sensor), the mean over an 8 min steady state was determined.

Results and discussion

The absolute temperatures from the model and surface T_{sk} sensors are shown in Figure 2. Differences from the unmodified (bare) model surface are subsequently reported as mean difference (95% confidence interval). Coverage with the custom thermistor and tape, iButton and tape, and the tape only caused small increases in the underlying subsurface temperature by 0.27°C (0.22 to 0.32°C), 0.16°C (0.10 to 0.22°C), and 0.24°C (0.22 to 0.27°C), respectively. Coverage with the Grant thermistor and tape and the iButton without tape caused decreases in subsurface temperature by -0.24°C (-0.52 to 0.05°C) and -0.69°C (-0.78 to -0.60°C), respectively. The temperature measured by a surface T_{sk} sensor was always cooler than the subsurface temperature: custom thermistor and tape -0.46°C (-0.51 to -0.40°C); grant thermistor, -1.77°C (-1.90 to -1.65°C); iButton and tape, -1.50°C (-1.55 to -1.46°C); iButton without tape, -2.62°C (-2.67°C to -2.58°C).

Figure 2. Directly subsurface temperature measured without surface modification (bare) and when modified by a skin temperature sensor or tape. Temperature of the respective skin temperature sensors are also shown. Data are mean \pm standard deviation with n=5 replicates for each. The dashed horizontal line represents the mean temperature in the bare condition ($31.93 \pm 0.02^\circ\text{C}$).

Conclusions

Using a novel skin simulant, results indicate that the attachment of surface T_{sk} sensors induced small to moderate modification of the directly subsurface skin simulant temperature. Further, the temperature measured by the surface T_{sk} sensor always measured lower, even when covered by a tape attachment. The implications of considering perfusion warrant consideration for further analysis.